

(Laws of Sharia rulings and issues of the branches of jurisprudence.) قوانين الأحكام الشرعية ومسائل الفروع الفقهية

also known as “Qawanin al-Ahkam al-Shar’iyah wa Masa’il al-Furu’ al-Fiqhiyah”, “قوانين الفقهية في تلخيص مذهب المالک و التنبيه على مذهب الشافعية و الحنفية و الحنبلية”

By Bilyaminu Muhammad, Umaru Musa 'Yar-Adua University Katsina, Nigeria

Entry tags: Religious Group, Arabic, Text, Language, Islamic Traditions, Fiqh

The text was an Islamic religious encyclopedia that discussed most aspects of the Islamic Religion right from the theology, which made a vivid explanation of the general belief system of Islam. Other sections presented an analysis of the system of worship starting from the prayer (Salat), Fasting, charity (Zakat and Sadaqh), Pilgrimage (Hajj and Umrah), which constitute the second aspect of the pillars of Islam. Another area presented by the text is the principles of social interaction (Mu'amalat), which centered on marital affairs, inheritance, commercial transactions, legal justice, and others. The text extends discussions on the Islamic history to present the biography of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) and the history of the subsequent caliphate of the Omayyad and Abbasid dynasties. Likewise! The text espatiated ethics and moral guidance of Islam. The text was considered a significant Maliki jurisprudence applicable in the Western Islamic world, which Sokoto and some caliphates considered as an official canon for the religious appears in the environs under their control. Furthermore the context of the book is presently applied in the Islamic world.

Date Range: 1804 CE - 1903 CE

Region: Sokoto

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Benin, Burkina Faso, Niger, Togo, Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon

Sokoto around 1870, during the reign of Ahmadu Rufai. Adapted from AbdurRahman AbdulMoneim [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_\(cropped\).pr](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_(cropped).pr)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Muhammad, J. (2010). Qawanin li Ahkam al-Shar’iyah wa Masail al-Furu’ al-Fiqhiyah. Dar ibn Hazam Beirut Lebanon.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: https://www.alukah.net/manu/files/manuscript_6347/makhtotah.pdf

– Source 1 Description: محمد بن أحمد بن محمد. (750هـ). قوانين الأحكام الشرعية ومسائل الفروع الفقهية. مكتبة جامعة الملك سعود

– Source 2 URL: <https://feqhup.com/uploads/145451530604325.pdf>

– Source 2 Description: محمد بن أحمد بن محمد. (750هـ). قوانين الفقهية في تلخيص مذهب المالک و التنبيه على مذهب الشافعية و الحنفية و الحنبلية. دار ابن حزم

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/boni-jazi>

– Source 1 Description: أحمد م. (2011). شرح القوانين الفقهية لابن جزي

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specify type of paper

– Specify: White colored paper

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

- ↳ Tomb
– No
- ↳ Cemetery
– No
- ↳ Temple
– No
- ↳ Shrine
– No
- ↳ Altar
– No
- ↳ Devotional marker
– No
- ↳ Cenotaph
– No
- ↳ Church
– No
- ↳ Mosque
– Yes
- ↳ Synagogue
– No
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
– No
- ↳ Monument
– No
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– Yes

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: Bookshops

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

- ↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?
 - No
- ↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?
 - No
 - Notes: Both the political officials and religious officials stand independent.
- ↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...
 - No
- ↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Present full-time?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Present part-time?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?
 - No
 - ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– Yes

Notes: Most of the religious specialist belongs to Hausa and Fulani ethnic groups.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

Notes: Religious specialists engaged in other activities apart from the religious service in the region.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

Notes: Some specialists are judges, some are Imams, and some are teachers.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– Yes

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 30000000

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Number: 18000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 7000000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 18000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Deathrate and Birthrate.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– Number: 90

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 10

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 18000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Birthrate and Deathrate.

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

– Small religious group (trying to be organized-controlled by larger religious group)

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– Yes

Notes: Scholarly notions relied on the directives of the Islamic precepts, while the audience's opinions might be derived from the cultural beliefs of the region.

↳ How might emic and scholarly (anthropological) assessments of the audience differ?

– Specify: Scholastic goes strictly on the directives of the precepts, even if it sounds contrary to the norms of society.

↳ How might emic and scholarly (anthropological) assessments of the audience be similar?

– Specify: The opinion might go similar in as far as the audience got convinced with the opinion of the scholars.

Notes: The assessment could be the same whenever the audience is convinced.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The reward will be received in the hereafter.

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for all adherents?
– Yes

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for all adherents?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?
– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?
– Yes

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?
– Yes

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?
– No
Notes: Proselytizing could be done anywhere.

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?
– Yes
Notes: Normative proselytizing is aimed at the entire non-Muslims.

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?
– No

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?
– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– No

↳ Is it read?

– No

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: The text served as a guide in ritual practices of prayer (Salat), Fasting, Charity, and Pilgrimage.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– No

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– No

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: The prayer takes place at the mosque through recitation of the portion of the Qur'an, standing, bowing, prostration, and sitting.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

Notes: Some versions of the text are accompanied by art on the cover page of the book.

↳ Calligraphy?

– Yes

Notes: Calligraphy and the text's cover page designation.

↳ Illustrations?

– No

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text is printed in many variants at different printing presses.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

Notes: Some versions come with minimal explanations of complex terms.

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: The document is included in the body of work on Islamic jurisprudence.

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Codified law of Islam.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is there an institutionalized police force whose behavior is dictated by the legal

code?

– Yes

↳ Is there an institutionalized judicial system whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

↳ Does the text in question specify institutionalized punishment?

– Yes

↳ Execution?

– Yes

Notes: Execution is for individuals who unlawfully killed another person.

↳ Exile?

– Yes

Notes: Exile is reserved for armed thieves who have stolen the property of others without harming anyone.

↳ Corporal punishments?

– Yes

Notes: The fornicators are sentenced to 100 lashes.

↳ Ostracism?

– Yes

↳ Seizure of property?

– Yes

↳ Are there any established institutionalized rewards specified in the text?

– No

Notes: The promised reward is received in the hereafter.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

↳ Planting?

– No

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

↳ Harvest?

– No

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– Yes

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– Yes

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– No

↳ Marriage?

– No

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– No

↳ Divorce?

– No

↳ Warfare?

– Yes

↳ Funerary services?

– No

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

Notes: Eid al-Fitr and Eid al-Kabir festivals.

↳ Frequency of festivals?

– Specify: 2

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

– All members

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

– number: 5000

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– No

↳ Pilgramages?

– Yes

↳ How strict are the stipulations regarding pilgrimage?

– obligatory for some

↳ Is encouraging pilgrimages a primary reason for the existence of the text?

– No

Notes: Many reasons are behind the existence of the text apart from the pilgrimage.

↳ Are pilgrimages guided by the text associated with particular life events?

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage guided by this text involve/follow major routes/roads?

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance of the routes guided by the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the pilgrimage conducted by walking or by other means?

– Yes

↳ Feasting?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– No

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Yes

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Yes

Notes: The language of the afterlife is agreed as Arabic.

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions in the debate?

–Specify: Arabic language is the debate's unanimity position.

↳ What are the historically minority positions?

–Specify: The minority view is that languages apart from Arabic are acceptable.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: The corpse is washed and shrouded before the burial.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: The supreme High God creates other creatures.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Yes
- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
– Yes
- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Yes
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
– Yes
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes
- ↳ Can reward
– Yes
- ↳ Can punish
– Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– Yes
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– Yes
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
– No
- ↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: The Supreme High God Falls the rain.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: The Supreme High God communicates to living by Intuition.

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: The Supreme High God communicates to living by Intuition.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– No

- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living
- No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
- No

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
- No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
- Yes

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
- Yes

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
- Yes

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
- No

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
- No

- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
- Yes

- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
- Yes

- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
- No

- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Angels communicate to prophets on the directives of the Supreme High God.

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Inspiration.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Notes: Jinns have a desire for food.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Talking.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Mysterious?

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s)

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

↳ Adultery

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings record sin against the act of adultery.

↳ Incest

– Yes

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– Yes

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– Yes

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– Yes

Notes: A reward is being awarded for lawful sexual practices.

↳ Other sexual practices

– Yes

Notes: Other illegal sexual practices are prohibited.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

–Specify: Animals.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: A reward is only awarded by Angels on the directives of the supreme High God.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– Yes

↳ Other purpose

–Specify: Messiah appears to establish justice.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The actual time is not known to all except him the highest.

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

- ↳ Divine judgment event
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - No
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - No
 - Notes: The after-death life is permanent, not temporal.
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - No
- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
 - Specify: Divine judgment.
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
 - No
 - Notes: Only God would survive the eschaton.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
 - Yes

- ↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Yes

- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical)
– Yes
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– Yes
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: Except for the unmarried persons.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– Yes

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 3

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Number of participants: 1000

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 2

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– Yes

Notes: Obligatory and voluntary charity (Zakat and Sadaqah).

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Notes: Charity.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Yes

Notes: The text creates room for the acquiring of wisdom, which does not necessarily come from the direction of the religion.

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: Education is for both sexes.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– No

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– Yes

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– Yes

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

- ↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?
– No
- ↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?
– Yes
- ↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?
– Yes
- ↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?
– Yes
- ↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?
– Yes
- ↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?
– No
- ↳ Other form of regulation of public works?
– Specify: Administration.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

- ↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?
– Yes
- ↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?
– No
- ↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?
– Yes

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text separated chapter seven for warfare.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– Yes

↳ Power to conscript?

– Yes

↳ Maintain a full-time military corps (E.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

↳ Maintain a standing army?

– Yes

↳ Particular types of training/readiness?

– Yes

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– Yes

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– Yes

↳ Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

- ↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?
 - Yes

- ↳ Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]
 - Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

- ↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?
 - Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Bibliography

General References

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